

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CHANGES IN THE POPULATION NUMBER AND THEIR DYNAMICS IN THE MODERN STAGE OF NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

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Abstract

The article reflects the changes in the population of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic during the period 1999-2024. The article also analyzes the statistical data on the urban and rural population, the gender composition of the population, and mentions the presence of positive changes and trends in the population of the autonomous republic due to demographic, socio-economic, national-cultural and other factors.

Keywords: population, urban population, rural population, gender composition of the population, men, women.

The land of Nakhchivan, which is the ancient and eternal land of Azerbaijan, with an ancient and rich history, culture and traditions of multi-civility statehood, was one of the cradles of human civilization, and was historically considered one of the trade, craft, science and culture centers of the East. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is an integral part of the Republic of Azerbaijan, is located in the south - west belt of the Lesser Caucasus, in the south - east of the Transcaucasia plateau. Its territory stretches 158 km from north – west to south – east, and 75 km from north to south. It borders the Republic of Armenia from the north and northeast (246 km.), the Islamic Republic of Iran from the south and southwest (204 km.), and the Republic of Turkey from the southwest (15 km.). The total length of these borders is 465 kilometers. The territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is 5,5 thousand square kilometers, the population is 468.6 thousand people (January 1, 2024). 166.2 thousand people or 35,5% of the population live in urban areas, and 302,4 thousand people or 64,5% live in rural areas. 234,0 thousand people or 49,9% of the population are men, and 234,6 thousand people or 50,1% are women. The population density is 85 people per square kilometer. According to the population census of 2019, 99,72% of the population of the autonomous republic was made up of Azerbaijanis, and the rest – Russians, Kurds and representatives of other nations. In 2019, the average life expectancy of the population in the autonomous republic was 76,6 years for men and 80,7 years for women. Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic includes the capital city of Nakhchivan, which is a major industrial, scientific and cultural center, and 7 administrative districts – Sharur, Babek, Ordubad, Julfa, Kangarli, Shahbuz and Sadarak. These regions include 6

cities (Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Julfa, Sharur, Shahbuz and Babek), 9 settlements and 203 rural settlements [3, 4, 5].

Since the population and the economy are elements of a single social organism, in order for social production to occur and continue harmoniously in all societies, only a certain number of people with physical and mental abilities, health, education, knowledge and skills, qualifications, professional training, moral qualities and it is necessary to have intellectual human potential with culture [1, p. 6]. Since the population consists of people, and the demographic events are the facts related to individual people, the demographic events also depend on the size of the population and its structure. Changes in the population are reflected in demographic events also depend on the size of the population and its structure. Changes in the population are reflected in demographic processes, and changes in the demographic processes are reflected in the natural reproduction indicators of the population, and these, in turn, are reflected in the changes in the dynamics of movement of the population as a whole and its important component, labor force resources.

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is one of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan with unique demographic development characteristics. According to the data of the first national population census conducted in the independent Republic of Azerbaijan on January 27, 1999, the number of people living here was 354,1 thousand people. 95,1 thousand people or 26,9% of them lived in urban areas, and 259.0 thousand people or 73,1% lived in rural areas. In that period, 174,5 thousand people or 49,3% of the population of the autonomous republic were men, and 179,6 thousand people or 50,7% were women.

Distribution of the population in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic by gender and number (thousand of people at the beginning of the year)

years	Population size (thousand people)	including		For the whole population, in percentage		including		For the whole population, in percentage	
		city	village	city	village	men	women	men	women
1999	354,1	95,1	259,0	26,9	73,1	174,5	179,6	49,3	50,7
2000	358,8	96,2	262,6	26,8	73,2	177,0	181,8	49,3	50,7
2001	363,1	97,1	266,0	26,7	73,3	179,2	183,9	49,4	50,6
2002	366,9	97,8	269,1	26,7	73,3	181,1	185,8	49,4	50,6
2003	370,4	98,9	271,5	26,7	73,3	181,6	188,8	49,0	51,0
2004	373,9	110,1	263,8	29,4	70,6	186,0	187,9	49,7	50,3
2005	377,8	110,9	266,9	29,4	70,6	187,3	190,5	49,6	50,4
2006	382,1	111,6	270,5	29,2	70,8	189,7	192,4	49,6	50,4
2007	386,0	112,3	273,7	29,1	70,9	191,7	194,3	49,7	50,3
2008	391,8	114,2	277,6	29,1	70,9	193,0	198,8	49,3	50,7
2009	397,3	115,4	281,9	29,0	71,0	197,8	199,5	49,8	50,2
2010	402,4	116,7	285,7	29,0	71,0	200,0	202,4	49,7	50,3
2011	410,1	119,5	290,6	29,1	70,9	204,2	205,9	49,8	50,2
2012	418,5	121,7	296,8	29,1	70,9	208,2	210,3	49,7	50,3
2013	427,2	123,9	303,3	29,0	71,0	212,5	214,7	49,7	50,3
2014	435,3	127,2	308,1	29,2	70,8	216,7	218,6	49,8	50,2
2015	439,8	128,2	311,6	29,1	70,9	219,1	220,7	49,8	50,2
2016	444,4	131,0	313,4	29,5	70,5	221,6	222,8	49,9	50,1
2017	449,1	132,4	316,7	29,5	70,5	224,1	225,0	49,9	50,1
2018	452,8	133,6	319,2	29,5	70,5	226,0	226,8	49,9	50,1
2019	456,1	134,5	321,6	29,5	70,5	227,7	228,4	49,9	50,1
2020	459,6	135,6	324,0	29,5	70,5	229,6	230,0	50,0	50,0
2021	461,7	163,4	298,3	35,4	64,6	230,6	231,1	49,9	50,1
2022	463,1	164,0	299,1	35,4	64,6	231,4	231,7	50,0	50,0
2023	465,7	165,0	300,7	35,4	64,6	232,6	233,1	49,9	50,1
2024	468,6	166,2	302,4	35,5	64,5	234,0	234,6	49,9	50,1

Note: The table was compiled by the author based on the materials of the Statistics Committee of Nakhchivan AR.

As in our country, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the achievements in the economic field have created new opportunities for the development of the social field. Thus, in the autonomous republic sustainable development covering all areas of the economy, as well as comprehensive development of social areas and health care system, improvement of the volume and quality of communal, service and social infrastructure provision, the activity of industrial enterprises was not restored and the creation of new production enterprises, in the direction of the development of the agricultural sector the implementation of complex measures, the creation of new jobs, the increase of the employment level of the population, the reduction of poverty and the successful implementation of other socio-economic measures resulted in positive changes in the population. Thus it is clear from the dynamics of the changes in the total number and gender composition of the population of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the number of urban and rural population in the period 1999-2024, that the population of the autonomous republic increased by 114,5 thousand people, or 32,3% during that period, from 354,1 thousand people to 468,6 thousand people, including 71,1 thousand people or 74,8% increase in urban areas from 95,1 thousand people to 166,2 thousand people, also the rural areas 43,4 thousand people or 16,8% increased from 259,0 thousand

people to 302,4 thousand people, also the number of men increased by 59,5 thousand people to 34,1% from 174,5 thousand people to 234,0 thousand people, and the number of women increased by 55 thousand people or it increased by 30,6% from 179,6 thousand people to 234,6 thousand people. The increase in the number of population in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is related to the change in the demographic development indicators that are the result of socio-economic, national-cultural and other factors existing in the autonomous republic.

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